

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

3 MATILDE National Workshops

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Deliverable 7.4

3 National Workshops

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Summary

This document presents the three reports by the research team that work on the German, Scottish and Spanish case studies. They present main information about the three national workshop held between April and May 2022 to divulgate the Toolkit for Practitioners and Decision-makers' Self-assessment on their work for migrants' integration.

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Report from the German Research Team

Online workshop (Zoom) on Monday, March 21st (2 pm) with the partnership of local partner TAT and with the participation of various stakeholders from at least eight Federal States.

Team of the Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU): Dr Stefan Kordel,

Dr Tobias Weidinger and David Spenger

Local partner TAT: Anne Güller-Frey

Selection of the format, invitation and participants

The **online format** was chosen for the national workshop after consulting our local partner TAT and the head organization of IQ (Integration through Qualification). IQ is a funding programme of the Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs (BMAS)¹ that aims at improving employment opportunities for people with a migration history. It consists of 16 regional networks (one for each federal state or *Land*) that focus i.e. on counselling with regard to the recognition of foreign credentials as well as of five competence centres dealing with migrant-specific issues, i.a. vocational German language, migrant entrepreneurship or intercultural opening and anti-discrimination.

Both actors mentioned above were of the opinion that an online format would reach a wider audience, since people do not have to travel and can better squeeze the event into their everyday work schedules. Accordingly, an invitation

¹ The BMAS also draws on ESF funds.

to the MATILDE national workshop was shared by our local partner TAT in the course of the regular IQ newsletter.

At the online workshop, 19 **participants** could be welcomed, thereof 13 female and six male. They originated from at least eight different federal states: Bavaria, Berlin, Hesse, Lower Saxony, North-Rhine Westphalia, Rhineland-Palatinate, Saarland and Schleswig-Holstein. The participants' backgrounds were very diverse, too: counselling centres for Third-Country Nationals (TCNs), the Federal Employment Agency, the Chamber of Crafts, a Federal Research Institute and a recruiting agency.

Structure and contents of the event

Moderated by Stefan Kordel, the two hours event was structured as following (see picture 1): After the presentation of the research team and local partner TAT, a short introduction of MATILDE project and the German case study was given. Then, the most important results with regard to recruiting and onboarding of TCNs in companies in rural and mountainous areas were presented and subsequently discussed with the audience. After a short break, FAU continued to introduce the findings with regard to the retention of TCNs in companies and rural and mountain areas as well as our proposed recommendations for action. Following from that, participants were invited and explicitly encouraged to comment on the recommendations. Finally, Anne Güller-Frey from TAT shared experiences from her good practice-example, i.e. the 'Bavarian skilled workers forum' (*Bayerisches Fachkräfteforum*). The presentation was shared afterwards among participants via email.

Picture 1: Screenshot Agenda

Topics of discussion

With regard to **recruiting and onboarding of TCNs**, participants commented that on part of skilled TCNs, many do not want to live in rural areas due to lacking communities, migrant organisations and specific food stuff. Therefore, it was considered difficult among some participants, if recruiting agencies instead of TCNs themselves decide about the place of work. One recruiting agency highlighted the matching process they apply and pointed towards the surplus of the envisaged seal of quality for recruiting agencies. On part of rural entrepreneurs, in contrast, participants reported of a hesitation to recruit TCNs, which was considered to be related to racism, a fear that TCNs would leave the company sooner or later or a lack of (legal) knowledge. The stakeholders highlighted that companies need support in terms of bureaucracy and visa processes. With regard to this, the Federal Employment Agency, for instance, reported of an implemented round table with companies who recruit from abroad that aims at overcoming these obstacles. Further aspects discussed were lack of time for onboarding and intercultural opening due to a lack of workers and high rate of COVID-19 related sick leaves especially in the (health)care sector, insufficient language competencies of TCNs and the importance of language acquisition prior and after entering Germany as well as difficulties with regard to access to housing and mobility to the workplace.

With regard to the **retention of TCNs in rural and mountain areas**, participants highlighted the importance of encounters between immigrants as well as between immigrants and local inhabitants, e.g. at the vocational school or at clubs and associations.

Recommendations for action, finally, revolved around several topics, such as

- the necessity to prepare companies, schools and societies in rural and mountain areas for the arrival of TCNs, e.g. by means of the establishment of intercultural opening processes or support groups)
- a better marketing of the destination country Germany, the apprenticeship, the specific sector/company and rural and mountain areas in the countries of origin, drawing on social networks, twinning agreements with schools or cities/municipalities, fairs and on-site events as well as internships or trial works.

Report from the Spanish Research Team

Workshop held on **April 7, 2022. Online. 10.30 to 12.45 a.m.**

16 participants: responsables of Social care, Housing, Health, Migration and Regional planning Departments of the Public Administration at National and Regional levels (Autonomous Communities represented: Aragón, Asturias, Navarra, Catalonia, Castilla y León and Castilla-La Mancha). Also, national representants of the section of Migration from one 'Trade Union', also from CARITAS and CEPAIM Foundation (independent organization for migrants issues and welcoming of immigrants).

Among them, we highlight the presence of:

- The currently attached to the Secretary of State for Migration of the Ministry of Inclusion, Social Security and Migrations,
- The Ex-Secretary of State for Migration between 2020 and 2021, with the government of Pedro Sánchez.
- Current Deputy General Director of Analysis, Planning and Coordination, of the General Directorate for the Demographic Challenge, Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge.

Organization of workshop:

- 1) Presentation of MATILDE-project (2 min.), round for presentation of participants (20 min.), and objectives of the workshop (3 min.).

- 2) Presentation of the Diagnosis carried out and the Proposals obtained from the analysis and fieldwork, divided into 5 themes -1 to 5- (showed with Power Point) (25 min.).
- 3) Intervention round and presentation-discussion of proposals generated by the participants, by thematics (85 min.).

Report from the Italian Team (UK Case Study)

Online workshop (Microsoft Teams) on Wednesday, May 12th with the partnership of COSLA and the participation of officers from the Scottish Local Authorities.

University of Parma Research Team: Dr Michele Bianchi, Dr Maria Luisa Caputo, and Prof Simone Baglioni.

As part of the MATILDE project milestones, the University of Parma research team organized an online workshop with officers from the Scottish Local Authorities to illustrate the toolbox for the practitioners' and decision-makers' self-assessment of their work for migrants' integration.

COSLA (Convention of Scottish Local Authorities), is the main partner for the Scottish case study. It is the national association of the Scottish councils and works to promote their interest and support their functioning. Dr Lorraine Cook and Mrs Anna Tajsiak have assisted the research team since the beginning of the project; they are experts in policy on migration and coordinate projects and schemes for refugees and asylum seekers by Scottish Local Authorities.

Due to the necessity to gather a consistent number of participants, the location in remote areas of many of them, and the possibility to optimize the working time by avoiding a journey to a physical venue (e.g. COSLA headquarter in Edinburgh), we agreed with our partner to have this workshop online. The choice has resulted in positive because we have had the attendance of 18 officers from all over Scotland.

This event was centred on the presentation of the toolkit elaborated by Dr Marika Gruber, Dr Christina Lobnig, Dr Jessica Pöcher, and Dr Kathrin Zupan from the Carinthia University of Applied Sciences. The toolbox aims to enhance

practitioners' and decision-makers' capacity to self-assess their organizations, communities, and regions in the field of migrants' integration; the tools provide the possibility to collect information and data, engage citizens and local agencies, and involve newcomers in the comprehension of integration processes.

After the welcoming from the COSLA team, the University of Parma researchers introduced the principal goals of the project. Dr Maria Luisa Caputo explained the main results from the fieldwork held in the Outer Hebrides and the qualitative and quantitative analysis carried out on the Scotland migration system and conditions. Dr Michele Bianchi introduced the toolbox explaining the importance that MATILDE gives to the collaboration and partnership among the academic, practitioners, and policy sectors.

After the presentation, the group was subdivided into four virtual rooms; in each one, one of the experts introduced the features of a specific tool. This is the subdivision:

- Dr Maria Luisa Caputo: Mobility Mapping;
- Dr Michele Bianchi: Future Forum;
- Dr Lorraine Cook: Municipality Profile;
- Mrs Anna Tajsiaik: Video Talk;

During the 45 minutes in the separated groups, the participants had the occasion to ask for further information, share their thoughts about the tools, and assess the feasibility of their application in their local contexts.

After a 5 minutes break, the groups re-assembled in the main online room and each referent reported the main conclusions and feedback from the discussion. Then, the discussion moved to the hearing of local practices from the Scottish Local Authorities for self-assessment of work for migrants' integration.

The workshop was indeed an occasion to test the feasibility of these tools with practitioners and listen to their experiences and analysis. Although a general agreement on the importance of self-assessment and interest in these tools, the participants detected difficulty in implementing them. First, most of them already use similar tools to examine, plan and assess their daily work with migration. Second, they acknowledge the relevance of self-assessment in the working process but they do not have the time and resources to do that. Third, they see

a difficulty in migrants' involvement to assess the practices due to language barriers, individual shyness or fear to appear ungrateful. Generally, these officers agreed on the fact that their work is done under constant pressure, with restricted time compared to the enormity of the task and jumping from one crisis to another. The most shared image to describe their work is the "Firefighter"; they would like to implement more the methods for self-assessment but they cannot afford it.